

Achieving Latency-Aware V2V Communication with Distributed Antenna Systems

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Abstract—The future of accident-free road mobility hinges on reliable Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communication, especially as autonomous vehicles become more prevalent. The potential of the Distributed Antenna Systems (DAS) to improve throughput, data rates, and overall network efficiency has been well investigated and proved. However, its performance, especially in latency-aware dense vehicular networks, has not been studied. In this paper, we investigate the performance gain of DAS by equipping the vehicles with three antenna elements mounted on the roof and the bumpers. This results in a significant enhancement of communication reliability. Due to its low complexity and ease of implementation, the DAS relies on the use of selection combining technique allowing the exploitation of the most robust signal received by the antenna elements. Extensive system-level simulations for a highway scenario show that the DAS can significantly improve communication robustness and reliability, especially in scenarios with a large number of communicating vehicles. By effectively harnessing data from both antenna configurations, our study reveals an almost 60% improvement in terms of the achieved packet loss rate. Moreover, insights gained in this study could be used to support the trade-off analysis between additional antenna costs and V2V communication performance.

Index Terms—V2V communication, DAS, latency, packet loss, selection combining

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of autonomous vehicles necessitates robust and highly reliable Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communication, playing a crucial role in enhancing road safety, efficiency, and sustainability. Unlike traditional mobile broadband, Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) demands exceptionally high reliability and minimal latency, especially for critical applications like collision avoidance [1].

While standards like IEEE 802.11p (WAVE) [2] and ETSI ITS-G5 [3] facilitate diverse V2V applications, current research often focuses primarily on improving overall network performance metrics like throughput and resource allocation. This, however, overlooks a critical element of latency awareness in vehicular communication.

Messages transmitted between vehicles carry critical information, with varying latency requirements depending on their nature. Safety-critical messages, carrying information like collision warnings or emergency maneuvers, necessitate near-instantaneous delivery (≤ 100 ms) to prevent accidents [4]. On the other hand, non-safety critical messages, such as traffic

updates or entertainment data, can tolerate higher latencies (e.g. up to 500 ms) [5]. Typical messages in vehicular scenarios are transmitted at a rate of up to ten messages per second. However, especially for longer distances, the receiver does not have to decode every message to obtain the relevant information on time. By receiving at least one valid message out of four consecutive transmissions (every 100 ms), we achieve a maximum delay of less than 500 ms, which is comfortably within the latency requirements

Existing studies often focus on optimizing overall network performance, like efficiency or reliability, without fully considering the urgency of different message types. Thus, it becomes important to analyze the different latency requirements imposed by the current V2V scenarios, majorly the dense vehicular scenarios, for improving reliability. To enhance communication reliability, researchers have explored methods like multi-antenna systems at the receiver side [6]. Multi-antenna systems have proven to enhance the performance in these diverse scenarios, including fading and line-of-sight conditions, as demonstrated through packet-level selection diversity approaches in [7], but addressing these diverse latency requirements remains a gap.

Distributed Antenna System (DAS) emerges as a promising solution to bridge this latency gap [5]. By utilizing multiple antennas distributed across a vehicle, DAS offers advantages such as improved channel capacity, supporting higher data rates, and accommodating varying latency needs for messages. This research leverages the advantages of DAS to achieve latency-aware V2V communication. We investigate how DAS can be utilized to meet the specific latency requirements of different message types. By analyzing performance metrics like packet loss and probability of latency-aware reception rate, we aim to demonstrate how DAS can improve the quality and reliability of V2V communication, paving the way for a safer and more efficient autonomous vehicle ecosystem.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Sec. II describes DAS in combination with the diversity technique and its implementation in our research for latency studies. Next, Sec. III explains the details of the simulation setup. The evaluation metrics and the performance comparison of our approach to a classical monopole configuration are presented in Sec. IV. Finally, Sec. V concludes this document.

II. DISTRIBUTED ANTENNA SYSTEM WITH SELECTION COMBINING (DAS-SC)

To address the challenges posed by emerging V2V use cases such as safety and automated driving, the automotive industry widely acknowledges the need for DAS approaches [8]. By enabling the separate implementation of antenna units for transmission and reception, DAS strategies provide a compelling solution for overcoming the limitations of traditional single-antenna implementations of achieving varying latency requirements for different kinds of messages. Deploying the DAS system can provide a significant diversity gain, as the channel observed from each of the receiving antennas will be significantly uncorrelated compared to the singular antenna.

Previous studies [9] have explored DAS with diversity combining techniques in pedestrian-to-vehicle scenarios, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving overall signal quality and stability, but not considering the different latency requirements. Thus, the diversity schemes have been proven to improve reliability and address challenges like fading and interference in combination with DAS. However, current research lacks sufficient evidence to support their effectiveness in enhancing latency-aware communication systems.

While various diversity combining techniques exist, our study employs DAS coupled with Selection Combining (SC) at the MAC layer. SC is a fundamental technique in wireless communication systems aimed at enhancing signal reliability and reducing the impact of fading and interference. Multiple antennas are used to receive the same signal at the same time, and a selection mechanism is implemented where the antenna with the best instantaneous antenna gain is selected for further processing. This improves overall signal quality and enhances the system's ability to maintain a stable connection. In general, this is one of the most simplistic diversity approaches. A related approach is the use of multiple receivers, i.e., separate receivers for each antenna. However, within this paper, we purely focus on SC, as the use of multiple receivers would most likely lead to comparable results. Its low complexity and ease of implementation make it cost-effective for diversity reception in low-power devices with limited processing capabilities.

In conclusion, with our understanding, DAS with SC represents a valuable technology for enhancing V2V communication, offering both reliability and practicality.

III. SIMULATION SETUP

The simulation setup comprises a hybrid environment using SUMO [10] for road traffic simulation and OMNeT++ [11] for network simulation. The simulation also incorporates Veins [12], extending IEEE 802.11p-based vehicular communication with radio propagation models, antenna patterns, and truck engine models for realistic scenarios. The simulation scenario depicts a bi-directional highway section with two lanes per direction. A 3km central segment is used for statistical evaluation. The scenarios assume that there are consistently 50, 100, and 500 vehicles within the 3km range to cover different congestion levels. Half of the vehicles are moving in

Fig. 1: Simulated highway scenario

opposite directions, as shown in Fig. 1. Vehicle interference is considered within a maximum distance of 2600 m.

The study explores two vehicle antenna setups: "Mono" has a rooftop monopole serving as both transmitter and receiver, while "DAS" uses a rooftop monopole as the transmitter and adds dipole antennas on the front and rear bumpers as receivers.

Fig. 2: Antenna element locations on a vehicle with their radiation patterns

The antenna placement on all the vehicles for DAS is presented in Fig. 2. It also depicts the sample radiation pattern of all the antennas used, in the 2D plane, with all gain values expressed in terms of dBi. Because of design challenges and in alignment with one of the suggested scenarios presented in [8], receiving antennas have been positioned on both the front and rear bumpers. As far as diversity technique implementation is concerned, we simulated the dense highway scenario with Equal Gain Combining (EGC) and SC. Upon observation, we found no discernible difference in the performance of these techniques during single-hop broadcast transmissions, which is caused by the channel's extremely high interference level. Thus, throughout this study, to attain diversity gain at the receiver, we have implemented the SC method. Due to the interference-limited nature of our scenario, Maximum Ratio Combining (MRC) was not used since it is more appropriate for AWGN channels [13].

Table I shows the simulation parameters for the two scenarios.

TABLE I: Simulation parameters

Vehicular technology	IEEE 802.11p
Frequency	5.89 GHz
Transmission power	23 dBm
Message generation rate	10 msg/s
Message payload	1000 Bytes
Data rate	6 MBit/s
Channel propagation model	Highway propagation model
Antenna configurations	a) Monopole as Tx and Rx b) Monopole as Tx, dipole at the front and rear bumper as Rx
Highway length	6100 m \times 71 m
Number of vehicles	{50, 100, 500}
Simulation duration	310 s
Average vehicle speed	40 m/s

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we discuss the results obtained from the simulated scenario as well as an analysis of their values according to the number of vehicles involved. First, we present the evaluation metrics used to investigate communication performance. Based on these metrics, we evaluate the effect of distance and antenna configurations on packet reception in dense vehicular scenarios.

A. Evaluation Metrics

For quantifying the performance of V2V communication in the highway scenario with and without DAS, we concentrate on the below metrics influencing the overall communication performance:

- Packet Loss Rate (PLR) is calculated for all vehicles as the number of lost packets over the total number of sent packets.
- Latency-Aware Reception Rate (LARR) is defined as the ratio of the number of successfully received packets to the number of sent packets within a defined latency criteria.

We evaluated the LARR metric concerning the strict latency requirements of (≤ 100 ms) for critical safety-related messages and a relaxed latency of (≤ 400 ms) for non-critical alerts. A thorough understanding of this metric plays an important role, as timely information is crucial for road safety applications using V2V communication. Delays in transmitting or receiving vehicle state data can render it obsolete, hindering its ability to assist drivers in critical situations.

Additionally, our investigation delves into the underlying factors contributing to packet loss in both configurations.

B. Impact of Distance on Packet Loss

The average packet loss of both configurations is compared in Fig. 3 as the distance between transmitting and receiving vehicles increases in a V2V highway scenario. We can observe that the average PLR of the standard mono setup exhibits an exponential rise in PLR with distance due to inherent signal attenuation limitations, while the DAS configuration demonstrates a more gradual increase.

Remarkably, DAS extends the communication range to 2600 m, significantly surpassing close to the 1500 m limit

of the mono configuration. This is mainly achieved due to the higher antenna gain for the DAS. When considering the 500 m safety distance mandated by 5GAA [8] for critical applications, DAS maintains PLR below 10%, ensuring reliable reception of collision warning or emergency braking messages. This underscores DAS's effectiveness, especially when coupled with SC for optimal reception, effectively mitigating packet loss as vehicles move farther from the transmitter. The substantial PLR disparity between DAS (below 10%) and the mono configuration (over 25%) at a 500 m distance substantially impacts V2V communication scenario involving 50 vehicles. DAS effectively handles these low-density scenarios, allowing uninterrupted application usage and timely updates about surrounding events. Even at the maximum distance of 2600 m, DAS maintains a PLR below 40%, a significant improvement for safety-related applications.

As the number of vehicles increases, the likelihood of interference also rises. Interference can lead to packet collisions and loss, particularly for the mono configuration, which is more susceptible to interference from nearby vehicles. In these high-density scenarios (100 or 500 vehicles), the mono configuration experiences over 60% PLR, severely disrupting V2V communication.

DAS effectively mitigates this interference. The directional antenna patterns provide higher gain and effectively reduce the number of received devices per antenna by approximately half. This factor reduces PLR by 20% in a 500-vehicle scenario, demonstrating DAS's ability to receive safety messages reliably. Notably, despite a fivefold increase in vehicle density from 100 to 500, PLR does not drastically rise due to the saturation caused by extreme interference from other vehicles.

Fig. 3: Average packet loss rate as a function of distance for both antenna configurations with 50, 100, and 500 vehicles.

Fig. 4: Probability of receiving at least one packet with a latency of max 100 ms as a function of distance for both antenna configurations with 50, 100, and 500 vehicles.

C. Impact of Distance on Packet Reception Probability

Fig. 4 analyses the probability of receiving at least 1 packet with the maximum latency of 100 ms with increasing distance in a V2V highway scenario for both configurations. As distance increases, the mono configuration demonstrates a remarkably decreased probability of receiving packets within the crucial 100 ms latency window. At 1500 m with 50 vehicles, there's over a 52% chance of missing packets entirely within this time frame.

If safety-critical messages are repeatedly lost, it can significantly extend the reaction time for drivers or autonomous vehicles to respond to potential hazards. With our approach of DAS-SC, we can substantially increase the probability of receiving the same packets within 100 ms delay by 50%, significantly enhancing reaction time for vehicles within the 1500 m range.

In a collision scenario where the following vehicle is 300 m behind the colliding vehicle, it will be very critical that the collision warning message reach the follower within 100 ms latency window, as the next collision warning message will be sent after 100 ms. If the system uses a mono configuration, with a success rate of 86% at 500 m, the situation becomes critical. A collision at any point can significantly disrupt the message, reducing its reception probability well below the 86% benchmark. This raises the risk of the follower vehicle not receiving the warning in time, potentially leading to a secondary collision.

In contrast, the DAS configuration offers a significant advantage. With a 93% success rate at 500 m, DAS provides a much higher chance of the message reaching the follower within the 100 ms window, even if a collision occurs. The key

Fig. 5: Probability of receiving at least one packet with a latency of max 400 ms as a function of distance for both antenna configurations with 50, 100, and 500 vehicles.

difference lies in the reliability of message transmission under collision conditions. While mono struggles in such scenarios, DAS maintains a high probability of delivering the warning promptly, potentially preventing further accidents.

The probability of adhering to the strict latency requirements of 100 ms at a higher number of vehicles of 100 and 500 is achievable by almost 60% using our three-element DAS-SC approach. With the standard monopole on rooftop configuration, it becomes quite difficult to maintain low latency needs, and the probability is reduced to almost 40% of receiving packets with 100 ms delay, which signifies a heightened risk of data loss, potentially leading to communication disruptions in safety-critical situations.

The mono configuration suffers a drastic decline in packet reception probability with latency at longer distances. While it exhibits an 86% success rate at 500 m, this plummets to near zero by 2000 m, rendering it inadequate for delivering safety-critical messages across extended ranges. Conversely, the DAS demonstrates significantly superior performance. Even at 2000 m, it maintains a 60% probability of delivering packets within 100 ms, showcasing its remarkable resilience in dense traffic conditions. This crucially ensures the timely and reliable transmission of safety information, a decisive advantage over the limited range and unreliable monopole system.

Critically, the near-zero success rate of mono at 2000 m raises serious concerns about its suitability for real-world deployments requiring long-range communication. Therefore, for applications demanding low latency and high reliability for safety-critical messages, DAS proves to be the far superior choice compared to the unreliable and limited-range monopole configuration.

Fig. 5 presents the probability of packet reception, where

calculated the likelihood of receiving at least a single packet out of a four-packet transmission group with a maximum latency of 400 ms.

Even at a shorter distance of 500 m with only 50 vehicles, the chance of receiving all four packets within 400 ms latency is only 10% higher with DAS compared to mono. This implies that for low-density scenarios and safe distances, the IEEE 802.11p standard is sufficient for the timely delivery of both critical and non-critical messages, making DAS potentially less advantageous.

However, as the distance increases, the mono configuration exhibits a quite rapid decrease in reception probability. In contrast, DAS effectively manages to maintain the packet reception with a probability of 80% which indicates that there would be fewer temporal gaps and the information can be effectively transmitted even if more than two packets are lost in a row.

Even in highly congested scenarios (100 and 500 vehicles), DAS demonstrates its effectiveness in mitigating packet loss, by increasing the probability of packet reception to above 70% even for longer distances. This consistent performance across different vehicle densities highlights the robustness of DAS in addressing the challenges of interference and collisions.

For mission-critical applications requiring guaranteed low-latency communication, our approach of DAS-SC can fulfill the latency requirements and achieve more than 90% reliability for safety-critical use cases. It is even able to handle and mitigate interference. The latency needs of the messages with traffic updates or entertainment data can also be fulfilled much more efficiently with the help of DAS by having more than 80% probability of receiving them timely.

D. Factors Contributing to Packet Loss

Based on the analysis above, we observe that the DAS outperforms the mono antenna configuration, especially for dense traffic density scenarios. To understand the reason behind that, we conduct an additional performance study by investigating packet loss types concerning vehicle density values.

Fig. 6 highlights the primary factors contributing to packet loss for the two antenna configurations under varying vehicle densities. For a low vehicle count of 50, introducing DAS significantly reduces packet loss due to collisions by nearly 50%. Additionally, DAS effectively enhances the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR), reducing the number of packets lost due to low SINR by approximately 3 dB. This improvement in collision mitigation and SINR enhancement leads to a substantial increase in the number of successfully received and decoded packets, bolstering the overall reliability of V2V communication.

As the vehicle density increases to 100 and 500 vehicles, the reduction in packet loss due to collisions or low SINR becomes less pronounced. In these densely populated scenarios, the likelihood of collisions escalates significantly as numerous transmitters compete for channel access, causing signal superposition and increased interference. As a result, packet loss primarily stems from collisions rather than low

Fig. 6: Main factors contributing to packet loss under varying vehicle densities.

SINR. While DAS effectively addresses low SINR-related packet loss, its impact on collision mitigation is limited due to the overwhelming presence of collisions. In these scenarios, there is no significant improvement in the number of successfully decoded packets compared to the mono configuration. Another factor aggravating collision rates is the hidden node problem. In this scenario, vehicles are unable to detect each other's transmissions due to interference from nearby vehicles, leading to undetected collisions and reduced packet reception, particularly in high-density environments like 500 vehicles. Furthermore, a saturation point is observed in the reduction of collisions and low SINR occurrences due to the assailing interference from surrounding vehicles. This saturation suggests that current mitigation strategies may reach their limitations in densely populated vehicular environments.

E. Overall Loss Comparison

To summarize, Fig. 7 provides a comprehensive performance comparison between the two antenna configurations in the most congested scenario involving 500 vehicles. We observed a significant reduction in PLR by almost 30% for the DAS configuration, significantly enhancing data reliability for safety-critical applications. The DAS configuration demonstrated superior performance by maintaining packet loss below 40% within the safety distance of 500 m. The likelihood of packets being not received within a latency of more than 100 ms is around 60% more when we use the mono configuration at a distance of 500 m as compared to DAS.

Even for larger distances beyond 1500 m, there is zero reception of packets with mono configuration whereas DAS sustains by still receiving more than 40% packets with a latency of 100 ms. With mono configuration, it will not be possible to even receive non-safety alerts at longer distances of

1500 m and beyond which shows its inability for long-distance vehicular communication. The DAS configuration effectively mitigates the situation, providing improvements in packet loss rate by over 50%, enabling timely updates about surrounding vehicle status even in highly congested environments.

V. CONCLUSION

This research investigated the effectiveness of a SC-based DAS in enhancing the latency-aware performance of V2V communication in dense vehicular scenarios by analyzing metrics like packet loss and latency-aware reception rate. Autonomous vehicles need a robust communication mechanism that guarantees the delivery of safety-critical messages with minimal latency to avoid potential collisions. According to our research, the use of DAS-SC can significantly contribute to this performance enhancement. Compared to mono, DAS-SC substantially reduced PLR, especially in dense scenarios with 500 vehicles. This improvement reached almost 60% at a distance of 500 m, ensuring reliable data transmission for safety-critical applications. Additionally, it doubled the communication range for successfully received packets compared to mono, reaching up to 2600 m. We observed enhanced LARR for latency-critical messages with DAS-SC and it notably increased the probability of receiving safety messages within a strict latency of 100 ms. This improvement reached 50% more compared to mono, ensuring timely response to critical situations like emergency braking. Furthermore, our investigation of factors contributing to this packet loss shows that with the help of DAS, we can significantly decrease the message collisions as the two antennas deployed will focus towards their maximum gain direction, which in turn can increase the number of successfully received and decoded packets. In scenarios with

a high number of vehicles, the primary cause of packet loss is collisions, a challenge that can be effectively mitigated through the application of advanced channel access techniques or resource allocation strategies. Concurrently, packet losses attributed to low SINR can be efficiently managed with the integration of DAS, resulting in a reduction of nearly 40%, even in high-density environments. This research demonstrates that DAS-SC is a promising technology for improving the latency-aware performance of V2V communication in dense vehicular scenarios. It is crucial to note that this enhanced performance necessitates a more intricate implementation and incurs higher costs, especially when juxtaposed with the use of a single antenna. However, the addition of a single antenna can augment performance by approximately 60%, making this implementation highly worthwhile in optimizing and ensuring safety in vehicular communication systems.

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Fig. 7: Average packet loss rate as a function of distance for both antenna configurations for 500 vehicles.